

Syntheses and characterization of coordination compounds of *N*-(2-mercaptoethyl)-4-(3'-carboxy-2'-hydroxyphenyl)-2-azetidinone

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Abstract : A dioxane solution of *N*-(2-mercaptoethyl)-3-carboxy-2-hydroxybenzylideneimine, L'H₃ (I) on reacting with chloroacetyl chloride in the presence of triethylamine, undergoes cyclization to form *N*-(2-mercaptoethyl)-4-(3'-carboxy-2'-hydroxyphenyl)-2-azetidinone, L'H₃ (II). A MeOH solution of L'H₃ reacts with Mn^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II}, Zn^{II}, Cd^{II}, Zr^{IV}, MoO₄²⁻ and UO₂²⁺ ions to form the complexes [M(L'H).MeOH]₂ (where M = Mn^{II}, Co^{II} or Ni^{II}), [Cu(L'H)]₂, [M'(L'H)] (where M' = Zn^{II}, Cd^{II}, MoO₄²⁻ or UO₂²⁺) and [Zr(OH)₂(L'H)]₂. The compounds have been characterized on the basis of elemental analyses, molar conductance, molecular weight, spectral (IR, UV-Visible) studies and magnetic susceptibility measurements. L'H₃ behaves as a dibasic tridentate OON donor ligand in [Cu(L'H)]₂, while it acts as a dibasic tetradentate OONS donor ligand in rest of the compounds. The complexes [M(L'H).MeOH]₂ (where M = Mn^{II}, Co^{II} or Ni^{II}), [Cu(L'H)]₂ and [Zr(OH)₂(L'H)]₂ are dimers, and the complexes [M'(L'H)] (where M' = Zn^{II}, Cd^{II}, MoO₄²⁻ or UO₂²⁺) are monomers. The dimeric complex [Cu(L'H)]₂ exhibits subnormal magnetic moment and is involved in antiferromagnetic exchange, while all other complexes are magnetically dilute. The octahedral structure for Mn^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, MoO₄²⁻ and UO₂²⁺ complexes, square planar structure for Cu^{II} complex, tetrahedral structure for Zn^{II} and Cd^{II} complexes, and pentagonal bipyramidal structure for Zr^{IV} complex have been suggested.

Keywords : Azetidinones, mercapto, dimetallic coordination compounds, paramagnetism, infrared spectra, UV-Visible spectra, coordination compounds.

Introduction

β-Lactams, the most versatile antibiotics used in medicines, are the 2-carbonyl derivatives of azetidine. The most widely used antibiotics such as cephalosporins, nocardicins and penicillins all possess β-lactam ring and the biological activities of these antibiotics are associated with the chemical reactivity of the β-lactam ring¹. Azetidinones are known to possess anticancer, analgesic, insecticidal, antimicrobial, anticonvulsant, anti-inflammatory, antitubercular, antifungal, sedatives and antidepressant activities². The study of transition metal complexes derived from the sulphur donor ligands is known for their carcinostatic, antibacterial and antifungal activities³. Sulphur donor ligands have been used as PVC

stabilizers, agrochemicals and anti-fouling paints due to their low phototoxicity and favourable environmental degradation⁴. A perusal of the literature reveals that very little work has been done on the coordination compounds of azetidinones⁵⁻⁷ and this is the first report on the coordination compounds of azetidinones containing a sulphur atom. In this paper, we report the syntheses and characterization of L'H₃ (II) and its Mn^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II}, Zn^{II}, Cd^{II}, Zr^{IV}, MoO₄²⁻ and UO₂²⁺ coordination compounds.

Results and discussion

N-(2-Mercaptoethyl)-4-(3'-carboxy-2'-hydroxyphenyl)-2-azetidinone, L'H₃ (II) was synthesized by the reaction of chloroacetyl chloride with *N*-(2-

mercaptoethyl)-3-carboxy-2-hydroxybenzylideneimine, LH₃ (I) in the presence of triethylamine in dioxane. The reaction of L'H₃ with appropriate metal salt/metal complex in 1 : 1 molar ratio in MeOH produces the coordination compounds, [M(L'H)·MeOH]₂ (where M = Mn^{II}, Co^{II} or Ni^{II}), [Cu(L'H)]₂, [M(L'H)] (where M = Zn^{II}, Cd^{II}, MoO₄²⁻ or UO₂²⁺) and [Zr(OH)₂(L'H)]₂. The coordination compounds are insoluble in H₂O, MeOH, EtOH, partially soluble in CHCl₃, Me₂CO, C₆H₆ and completely soluble in DMSO and DMF. They are non-electrolytes in DMF ($\Lambda_m = 2.5\text{--}9.7$ mho cm² mol⁻¹). The complexes [M(L'H)·MeOH]₂ (where M = Mn^{II}, Co^{II} and Ni^{II}) do not lose MeOH molecule on heating up to 120 °C. MeOH molecules are completely lost by heating Mn^{II}, Co^{II} and Ni^{II} complexes in an air oven at 173, 145 and 167 °C respectively and this indicates that MeOH molecules are coordinated to the respective metal ions and are not present as solvent crystallization.

The infrared spectra of LH₃ (I), L'H₃ (II) and the coordination compounds of II were recorded in KBr. LH₃ exhibits the $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$ (azomethine) stretch at 1632 cm⁻¹. This band disappears in L'H₃ and a new band due

to $\nu(\text{C}-\text{N})$ (β -lactam)⁸ appears at 1405 cm⁻¹ indicating the conversion of I into II. The formation of the azetidinone is further supported by the appearance of a new band due to $\nu(\text{C}-\text{Cl})$ (β -lactam)⁹ at 745 cm⁻¹. The $\nu(\text{C}-\text{N})$ (β -lactam) stretch of II shifts to lower energy by 20–35 cm⁻¹ in the complexes indicating the involvement of the N atom of β -lactam moiety towards coordination⁸. L'H₃ exhibits a strong band at 2850 cm⁻¹ due to the intramolecular H-bonded OH group of phenolic and/or carboxylic acid moieties. This band disappears in the complexes indicating the breakdown of H-bonding and subsequent deprotonation of the OH group followed by the involvement of phenolic and carboxylic acid O atoms towards coordination. The presence of a broad band at ~3400 cm⁻¹ and the decrease of $\nu(\text{C}-\text{O})$ (alcoholic) stretch of MeOH from 1034 cm⁻¹ to lower energy by 44–74 cm⁻¹ in [M(L'H)·MeOH]₂ (M = Mn^{II}, Co^{II} and Ni^{II}) indicate the involvement of the O atom of MeOH towards coordination¹⁰. A medium intense band at 2530 cm⁻¹ in II is assigned to the $\nu(\text{S}-\text{H})$ stretch¹¹. This band remains at the same energy in

Table 1. Analytical data of *N*-(2-mercaptoethyl)-4-(3'-carboxy-2'-hydroxyphenyl)-2-azetidinone and its coordination compounds

Compd.	Molecular formula	Molecular weight Found/(Calcd.)	Found/(Calcd.) %					
			M	C	H	N	S	Cl
L'H ₃ (II)	C ₁₂ H ₁₂ NO ₄ SCl	(301.5) 301.5 ^a	-	47.62 (47.76)	3.86 (3.98)	4.62 (4.64)	10.46 (10.61)	11.40 (11.77)
[Mn(L'H)·MeOH] ₂	Mn ₂ C ₂₆ H ₂₈ N ₂ O ₁₀ S ₂ Cl ₂	(761.6) 772.8 ^b	14.05 (14.21)	40.63 (40.37)	3.58 (3.62)	3.47 (3.62)	8.12 (8.28)	9.10 (9.19)
[Co(L'H)·MeOH] ₂	Co ₂ C ₂₆ H ₂₈ N ₂ O ₁₀ S ₂ Cl ₂	(809.2) 780.8 ^b	14.92 (15.09)	39.75 (39.96)	3.62 (3.59)	3.48 (3.59)	8.11 (8.20)	8.98 (9.09)
[Ni(L'H)·MeOH] ₂	Ni ₂ C ₂₆ H ₂₈ N ₂ O ₁₀ S ₂ Cl ₂	(763.6) 780.4 ^b	14.82 (15.04)	39.72 (39.98)	3.46 (3.59)	3.62 (3.59)	8.30 (8.20)	9.23 (9.10)
[Cu(L'H)] ₂	Cu ₂ C ₂₄ H ₂₀ N ₂ O ₈ S ₂ Cl ₂	(715.5) 726.0 ^b	17.20 (17.49)	39.40 (39.67)	2.68 (2.75)	3.93 (3.86)	8.95 (8.82)	9.64 (9.78)
[Zn(L'H)]	ZnC ₁₂ H ₁₀ NO ₄ SCl	(351.3) 364.9 ^b	17.60 (17.92)	39.58 (39.46)	2.82 (2.74)	3.78 (3.84)	8.60 (8.77)	9.82 (9.73)
[Cd(L'H)]	CdC ₁₂ H ₁₀ NO ₄ SCl	(427.6) 411.9 ^b	27.18 (27.29)	34.70 (34.96)	2.46 (2.43)	3.32 (3.40)	7.58 (7.77)	8.47 (8.62)
[Zr(OH) ₂ (L'H)] ₂	Zr ₂ C ₂₄ H ₂₄ N ₂ O ₁₂ S ₂ Cl ₂	(832.6) 849.4 ^b	21.10 (21.47)	33.73 (33.91)	2.75 (2.82)	3.21 (3.30)	7.31 (7.53)	8.28 (8.36)
[MoO ₂ (L'H)]	MoC ₁₂ H ₁₀ NO ₆ SCl	(417.8) 427.4 ^b	22.36 (22.44)	33.88 (33.69)	2.26 (2.34)	3.10 (3.28)	7.62 (7.49)	8.10 (8.31)
[UO ₂ (L'H)]	UC ₁₂ H ₁₀ NO ₆ SCl	(558.3) 569.5 ^b	41.82 (41.79)	25.06 (25.28)	1.85 (1.76)	2.38 (2.46)	5.54 (5.62)	6.10 (6.23)

Abbreviations : ^aMass spectral data, ^bRast method data.

Table 2. IR, reflectance spectral data (cm⁻¹) and magnetic moments of coordination compounds of II

Compd.	$\nu(\text{COOH})$	$\nu(\text{C-O})$ (phenolic)	$\nu(\text{C-N})$ (β -lactam)	$\nu(\text{C-O})$ (MeOH)	$\nu(\text{C-S})$ (thioalcoholic)	ν_{max}	Mag. moment (B.M.)
L'H ₃ (II)	1675	1520	1405	–	760	–	–
[Mn(L'H)·MeOH] ₂	1610	1550	1380	960	705	18320, 22760, 25290	5.84
[Co(L'H)·MeOH] ₂	1630	1540	1375	990	720	9100, 12990, 18800	4.70
[Ni(L'H)·MeOH] ₂	1635	1555	1385	970	695	9400, 16550, 25100	3.06
[Cu(L'H)] ₂	1615	1540	1370	–	760	17300	1.54
[Zn(L'H)]	1610	1530	1390	–	718	–	–
[Cd(L'H)]	1605	1530	1385	–	715	–	–
[Zr(OH) ₂ (L'H)] ₂	1635	1550	1370	–	704	–	–
[MoO ₂ (L'H)]	1620	1528	1385	–	720	–	–
[UO ₂ (L'H)]	1625	1530	1380	–	710	–	–

[Cu(L'H)]₂ indicating the non-involvement of the S atom towards coordination in this coordination compound. The $\nu(\text{C-S})$ (thioalcoholic) stretch¹¹ of II occurs at 760 cm⁻¹. This band remains at the same energy in [Cu(L'H)]₂ indicating the non-involvement of the S atom towards coordination. However, this band undergoes a negative shift by 40–65 cm⁻¹ in rest of the coordination compounds indicating the involvement of the S atom towards coordination¹¹. The $\nu(\text{C=O})$ (β -lactam) stretch^{6,7} of II occurring at 1730 cm⁻¹ remains unchanged in the coordination compounds suggesting the non-involvement of the O atom of β -lactam moiety towards coordination. The $\nu(\text{C=O})$ (carboxylic) stretch¹² of II (1675 cm⁻¹) shifts to lower energy by 40–70 cm⁻¹ in the coordination compounds indicating the involvement of the O atom of carboxylic group towards coordination. The $\nu(\text{C-O})$ (phenolic) stretch of II occurring at 1520 cm⁻¹ shifts to higher energy by ≤ 10 cm⁻¹ in [M(L'H)] (M = Zn^{II}, Cd^{II}, MoO₂²⁺ and UO₂²⁺) and by 20–35 cm⁻¹ in rest of the coordination compounds supporting the involvement of phenolic O atom towards coordination. The magnitude of the above shift of the $\nu(\text{C-O})$ (phenolic) stretch indicates the monomeric structure for [M(L'H)] (M = Zn^{II}, Cd^{II}, MoO₂²⁺ and UO₂²⁺) and the dimeric structure for the rest of the coordination compounds as in the event of a dimeric structure, the $\nu(\text{C-O})$ (phenolic) stretch shifts to higher energy by >10 cm⁻¹. The $\nu(\text{C-Cl})$ (β -lactam) stretch⁹ of II occurring at 745 cm⁻¹ remains unchanged in the coordination compounds indicating the non-involvement of the Cl atom of β -lactam moiety towards

coordination. The absence of a band in the region 835–955 cm⁻¹ due to the $\nu(\text{Zr=O})$ stretch in the present Zr^{IV} compound suggests its formulation as [Zr(OH)₂(L'H)]₂ and not as [ZrO(H₂O)(L'H)]₂. The presence of a broad band at 3450 cm⁻¹ and the appearance of a new medium intense band at 1140 cm⁻¹ due to the $\delta(\text{Zr-OH})$ bending mode also support the proposed structure of the present Zr^{IV} compound. The complex [MoO₂(L'H)] exhibits the $\nu_{\text{sy}}(\text{O=Mo=O})$ and $\nu_{\text{asy}}(\text{O=Mo=O})$ stretches at 910 and 940 cm⁻¹ respectively. These bands occur in the usual ranges $\nu_{\text{sy}}(\text{O=Mo=O})$ stretch 892–964 cm⁻¹ and $\nu_{\text{asy}}(\text{O=Mo=O})$ 842–928 cm⁻¹, reported for the majority of MoO₂²⁺ complexes. The presence of two bands due to the $\nu(\text{O=Mo=O})$ stretch is indicative of a *cis*-MoO₂ configuration as the complex with *trans*-MoO₂ structure shows only $\nu_{\text{asy}}(\text{O=Mo=O})$ stretch since the $\nu_{\text{sy}}(\text{O=Mo=O})$ stretch is IR inactive. The *cis*-MoO₂ structure forces the tetradentate ligand to coordinate in a non-planar fashion (III)¹³. The absence of a band at ~ 780 cm⁻¹ in the MoO₂²⁺ complex indicates the absence of an oligomeric chain with $\cdots\text{Mo}\cdots\text{Mo}\cdots\text{Mo}\cdots$ interaction. The complex [UO₂(L'H)] exhibits the $\nu_{\text{asy}}(\text{O=U=O})$ stretch at 905 cm⁻¹ and this band occurs in the usual range (870–950 cm⁻¹) observed for the majority of *trans*-UO₂^{II} compounds. On the basis of analytical data (Table 1), valence requirements and the infrared spectral studies, it is proposed that II behaves as a dibasic tridentate OON donor ligand in [Cu(L'H)]₂ and as a dibasic tetradentate OONS donor ligand in the rest of the coordination compounds. The new non-

ligand bands in the present coordination compounds in the low frequency region are assigned to the $\nu(\text{M-O})$ ($550\text{--}580\text{ cm}^{-1}$) and the $\nu(\text{M-N})$ ($430\text{--}455\text{ cm}^{-1}$) and these bands are in the expected order of increasing energy $\nu(\text{M-N}) < \nu(\text{M-O})$ ¹⁴.

The complexes being insoluble or sparingly soluble in common non-coordinating organic solvents, the solution electronic spectra could not be recorded and hence the reflectance spectra were recorded (Table 2). The complex, $[\text{Mn}(\text{L'H})\cdot\text{MeOH}]_2$ exhibits three bands at 18320 , 22760 and 25290 cm^{-1} due to ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(G)$, ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(G)$ and ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4A_{1g}(G)$ transitions, respectively in an octahedral environment¹⁵. The presence of three bands at 9100 , 12990 and 18800 cm^{-1} due to ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(v_1)$, ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4A_{2g}(v_2)$ and ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(v_3)$ transitions, respectively in $[\text{Co}(\text{L'H})\cdot\text{MeOH}]_2$ suggests an octahedral arrangement of L'H_3 around Co^{II} ions¹⁵. The v_3/v_1 value in the present Co^{II} compound is 2.06 and it lies in the usual range ($2.0\text{--}2.80$), reported for the majority of octahedral Co^{II} complexes¹⁵. The electronic spectral parameters for $[\text{Co}(\text{L'H})\cdot\text{MeOH}]_2$ were calculated using the standard method^{15,16} and the values are as follows : $Dq = 1021\text{ cm}^{-1}$, $B' = 721\text{ cm}^{-1}$, $\beta = B'/B = 0.74$, $\beta^0 = 26\%$ and $\text{CFSE} = -97.6\text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$. The reduction of Racah parameter from the free ion value of 971 cm^{-1} to 721 cm^{-1} and β^0 value of 26% indicate the covalent nature of the compound and the strong field nature of the tetradentate ligand **II**¹⁷. The complex, $(\text{Ni}(\text{L'H})\cdot\text{MeOH})_2$ exhibits three bands at 9400 , 16550 and 25100 cm^{-1} due to ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{2g}(F)(v_1)$, ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(F)(v_2)$ and ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(P)(v_3)$ transitions, respectively in an octahedral symmetry¹⁵. The v_2/v_1 value in the present Ni^{II} compound is 1.76 and it lies in the usual range ($1.60\text{--}1.82$), reported for the majority of octahedral Ni^{II} complexes¹⁵. The electronic spectral parameters for $[\text{Ni}(\text{L'H})\cdot\text{MeOH}]_2$ were calculated using the standard method^{15,16} and the values are as follows : $Dq = 940\text{ cm}^{-1}$, $B' = 806\text{ cm}^{-1}$, $\beta = B'/B = 0.78$, $\beta^0 = 22\%$ and $\text{CFSE} = -134.8\text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$. The reduction of the Racah parameter from the free ion value (1030 cm^{-1} to 806 cm^{-1}) and the β^0 value (22%) are indicative of the presence of covalent nature of the compound and the strong field nature of the tetradentate ligand **II**¹⁷. For a given ligand and given stereochemistry, the covalent character of the

corresponding Co^{II} and Ni^{II} coordination compounds is comparable since Co^{II} and Ni^{II} occupy the adjacent positions in the nephelauxetic metal ion series [i.e. $\text{Co}^{\text{II}} \sim \text{Ni}^{\text{II}}$]¹⁷. In the present Co^{II} and Ni^{II} coordination compounds, the β^0 values are quite comparable : $[\text{Co}(\text{L'H})\cdot\text{MeOH}]_2$; 26% ; $[\text{Ni}(\text{L'H})\cdot\text{MeOH}]_2$; 22% . For a given ligand and given stereochemistry, the spectrochemical series of metal ions on the basis of increasing $10Dq$ values is : $\text{Ni}^{\text{II}} < \text{Co}^{\text{II}}$. Our calculated $10Dq$ values indicate that the $10Dq$ values are in the expected order : $\text{Ni}^{\text{II}} < \text{Co}^{\text{II}}$. The greater negative CFSE value ($-134.8\text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$) for $[\text{Ni}(\text{L'H})\cdot\text{MeOH}]_2$ in comparison to that of $[\text{Co}(\text{L'H})\cdot\text{MeOH}]_2$ ($\text{CFSE} = -97.6\text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$) is as expected¹⁶. The presence of an asymmetric broad band at 17300 cm^{-1} due to the ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2A_{2g}$, ${}^2B_{2g}$ and 2E_g transitions in $[\text{Cu}(\text{L'H})]_2$ suggests a square planar arrangement of L'H_3 around Cu^{II} ion¹⁸. The absence of a band in the range $8000\text{--}10000\text{ cm}^{-1}$ precludes the presence of a tetrahedral structure.

The room temperature magnetic moments of the compounds are presented in Table 2. The magnetic moments of $[\text{Mn}(\text{L'H})\cdot\text{MeOH}]_2$, $[\text{Co}(\text{L'H})\cdot\text{MeOH}]_2$ and $[\text{Ni}(\text{L'H})\cdot\text{MeOH}]_2$ are 5.84 , 4.70 and 3.06 B.M. respectively. These values lie in the usual ranges : ~ 5.9 , $4.7\text{--}5.2$ and $2.9\text{--}3.4\text{ B.M.}$, reported for the majority of octahedral Mn^{II} , Co^{II} and Ni^{II} complexes respectively¹⁹. The Cu^{II} ion belongs to the $S = 1/2$ system and since the spin-orbit coupling constant for Cu^{2+} ion is negative¹⁷, the magnetically dilute Cu^{II} complexes are expected to exhibit magnetic moments higher than the spin-only value of 1.73 B.M. in the range $1.78\text{--}2.2\text{ B.M.}$ due to the presence of orbital contribution. The magnetic moment (1.54 B.M.) of the present Cu^{II} complex is substantially less than the above range of magnetic moment and this indicates the presence of antiferromagnetic type of magnetic exchange interaction¹⁷. The coordination compounds of Zn^{II} , Cd^{II} , Zr^{IV} , MoO_2^{2+} and UO_2^{2+} are diamagnetic as expected.

Thus, on the basis of analytical, molecular weight, spectral and magnetic studies, we suggest octahedral structure (**III**) for MoO_2^{2+} complex, (**IV**) for Mn^{II} , Co^{II} and Ni^{II} complexes, square planar structure (**V**) for Cu^{II} complex, tetrahedral structure (**VI**) for Zn^{II}

M = Mn^{II}, Co^{II} or Ni^{II}

M = Zn^{II}, Cd^{II}

and Cd^{II} complexes, pentagonal bipyramidal structure (VII) for Zr^{IV} complex and octahedral structure (VIII) for UO₂²⁺ complex.

Experimental

2-Aminoethanethiol hydrochloride [Aldrich]; copper(II) acetate monohydrate, zinc(II) acetate dihydrate, nickel(II) acetate tetrahydrate, acetylacetone, 1,4-dioxane [SD's]; cobalt(II) acetate monohydrate, cadmium(II) acetate dihydrate, dioxouranium(VI) acetate tetrahydrate, hexadecaquaactahydroxotetrazirconium(IV) chloride [BDH]; manganese(II) acetate tetrahydrate [Sarabhai]; ammonium molybdate(VI) tetrahydrate, Me₂CO, ethyl acetate, MeOH and petroleum ether (b.p. 60–80 °C) [Ranbaxy], and absolute EtOH [Bengal Chemical and Pharmaceuticals Ltd.] were used for the syntheses. Bis(acetylacetonato)-dioxomolybdenum(VI), hexadecaquaactahydroxo-tetrazirconium(IV) acetate and 3-formylsalicylic acid were synthesized by following the reported procedures^{10,20}.

The estimations of metal, chlorine and the sulphur contents of the respective compounds were carried out by the standard methods as reported earlier¹⁰. The carbon, hydrogen and nitrogen contents were determined by the Eager analyzer model-300 CHN analyzer. The molar conductances of the coordination compounds were determined in DMSO with the help of a Toshniwal conductivity bridge (CL01-02A) and dip type cell calibrated with KCl solutions. The molecular weights were determined by the Rast's method using diphenyl as the solvent. Infrared spectra were recorded in KBr (400–4000 cm⁻¹) on a Nicolet 5DX FT-IR spectrophotometer. Reflectance spectra were recorded on the Shimadzu UV-Visible spectrophotometer attached with a reflectance arrangement. The magnetic measurements were carried out at room temperature by the Gouy method using Hg[Co(NCS)₄] as the calibrant. The magnetic susceptibilities were corrected using diamagnetic corrections of the ligand and metal atoms and for temperature independent paramagnetism (TIP) term¹⁷.

Synthesis of Schiff base, LH₃ (I) :

A MeOH solution of anhydrous sodium acetate (0.82 g, 10 mmol in 25 mL) was added to a MeOH solution of 2-aminoethanethiol hydrochloride (1.135 g, 10 mmol in 30 mL). The mixture was stirred magnetically for 5 min

and the white precipitates of NaCl formed were filtered off. The filtrate was added to a MeOH solution of 3-formylsalicylic acid (1.66 g, 10 mmol in 50 mL) and the mixture was then stirred magnetically for 30 min at room temperature. The yellow coloured precipitate formed were suction filtered, washed with MeOH and dried under vacuum at room temperature over silica gel for 24 h. Yield 87%, Anal : (I, C₁₀H₁₁NO₃S) (Found : C, 53.58%; H, 4.78%; N, 6.36%; S, 14.46%. Calcd. : C, 53.33%; H, 4.89%; N, 6.22%; S, 14.22%); IR bands (KBr) : 2540 cm⁻¹ [ν(S–H)], 1660 cm⁻¹ [ν(C=O) (carboxylic)], 1535 cm⁻¹ [ν(C–O) (phenolic)], 1632 cm⁻¹ [ν(C=N) (azomethine)], 775 cm⁻¹ [ν(C–S) (thioalcoholic)].

Synthesis of N-(2-mercaptoethyl)-4-(3'-carboxy-2'-hydroxyphenyl)-2-azetidinone, L'H₃ (II) :

Chloroacetyl chloride (2.26 g, 20 mmol) was added drop by drop during a period of 2 h, while stirring constantly, to a dioxane solution of I (2.25 g, 10 mmol in 50 mL), in the presence of triethylamine (3.03 g, 30 mmol). Triethylamine hydrochloride formed was filtered off and the volume of the filtrate was reduced to 50%. The solution was kept aside for 24 h and the solid product formed was suction filtered, washed with dioxane and recrystallized from CHCl₃. The compound was dried as mentioned above. Yield 40%. Anal : (II, C₁₂H₁₂NO₄SCl) (Found : C, 47.62%; H, 3.86%; N, 4.62%; S, 10.46%; Cl, 11.40%. Calcd. : C, 47.76%; H, 3.98%; N, 4.64%; S, 10.61%; Cl, 11.77%); IR bands (KBr) : 2530 cm⁻¹ [ν(S–H)], 1730 cm⁻¹ [ν(C=O) (β-lactam)], 1675 cm⁻¹ [ν(C–O) (carboxylic)], 1520 cm⁻¹ [ν(C–O) (phenolic)], 1405 cm⁻¹ [ν(C–N) (β-lactam)], 760 cm⁻¹ [ν(C–S) (thioalcoholic)] and 745 cm⁻¹ [ν(C–Cl) (β-lactam)].

Syntheses of coordination compounds of L'H₃ (II) :

A MeOH solution (30–50 mL) of the appropriate metal salt/metal complex (10 mmol) was added to a MeOH solution (50 mL) of II (3.015 g, 10 mmol) and the mixture was then refluxed for 3–4 h. The solid products formed were suction filtered, washed with MeOH and were then dried as mentioned above. Yield 48–67%.

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